

Preoperative Assessment and Staging Classification of Adhesions in Difficult Laparoscopic Cholecystectomies: A Prospective Case-Control Study

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Abstract:

Background: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is the preferred surgical treatment for gallbladder diseases due to its minimally invasive nature and favorable outcomes. However, the presence of adhesions can significantly increase the difficulty of LC, leading to prolonged operative times and increased risk of complications. Accurate preoperative detection and staging of adhesions are crucial for anticipating surgical challenges and improving outcomes.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of preoperative detection and staging of adhesions in predicting the difficulty of laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Methods: Fifty participants (40 females aged 30-50 years and 10 males aged 45-55 years) were included. Preoperative imaging was used to detect and stage adhesions, which were later confirmed intraoperatively. The correlation between adhesion severity and surgical difficulty was assessed using chi-square and independent t-tests. Logistic regression analysis was performed to identify predictors of difficult LC.

Results: Adhesions were preoperatively detected in 28 participants (56%), with a high sensitivity (92.9%) and specificity (90.9%). Difficult LC was observed in 14 participants (28%), with a significant association between severe adhesions and surgical complexity ($p=0.003$). Logistic regression identified Stage 3 adhesions as a strong predictor of difficult LC (odds ratio = 4.8, $p<0.01$).

Conclusion: Preoperative detection and staging of adhesions using imaging techniques are effective in predicting the complexity of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The severity of adhesions is significantly associated with increased surgical difficulty, underscoring the importance of thorough preoperative evaluation.

Recommendations: Further studies are recommended to refine adhesion staging systems and explore additional imaging modalities that may enhance preoperative planning for laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, Adhesions, Preoperative Assessment, Surgical Difficulty, Imaging Techniques.

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Introduction

For the surgical management of gallbladder disorders, such as cholelithiasis and cholecystitis, laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is the gold standard. It has many benefits over open surgery, including less discomfort following surgery, shorter hospital stays, and faster recovery. Even yet, LC can be difficult in some circumstances, especially when adhesions are present, despite the procedure being minimally invasive. Those who have had prior abdominal surgeries, inflammation, or other illnesses are more likely to have adhesions, which are fibrous bands that develop between tissues and organs. These adhesions can make laparoscopic surgery (LC) much more challenging, resulting in longer operating periods, a higher percentage of

conversions to open surgery, and a higher risk of complications [1].

Planning and carrying out a successful surgical procedure depend heavily on the early detection and precise staging of adhesions.

When organising and carrying out a successful laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC), early adhesion identification and precise staging are essential. Preoperative adhesion detection has been made easier by developments in imaging technologies like magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT), and ultrasound. By evaluating the degree and character of adhesions, these techniques assist surgeons in anticipating possible

challenges and customising their surgical strategy accordingly. Even with these improvements, preoperative adhesion assessment is still difficult, and there isn't always a clear association between imaging results and intraoperative problems [2].

Enhancing preoperative adhesion detection accuracy and creating staging systems with improved surgical outcome prediction have been the main goals of recent research. Diffusion-weighted MRI, for example, has been shown in a study by Kim et al. (2019) to improve adhesion detection sensitivity and specificity, especially in situations of severe adhesions [3]. Similarly, a novel staging approach based on CT findings was proposed and demonstrated promising results in laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) complexity prediction [4]. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of preoperative detection and staging of adhesions in predicting the difficulty of laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a prospective case-control.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, over 18 months, from Dec. 2022 to June 2024.

Participants: A total of 50 participants were included in the study, consisting of 40 females aged 30 to 50 years and 10 males aged 45 to 55 years. Participants were selected based on their eligibility for laparoscopic cholecystectomy due to gallbladder disease.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 30 to 55 years undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.
- Patients with a clinical diagnosis of gallbladder disease requiring surgical intervention.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of prior abdominal surgeries.
- Patients with a known diagnosis of peritonitis or generalized sepsis.

- Patients with severe comorbid conditions that contraindicate laparoscopic surgery.
- Pregnant women and patients under 30 years of age or over 55 years of age.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients were randomly assigned to the case and control groups. The case group consisted of patients with preoperatively detected adhesions, while the control group included patients without detected adhesions. Blinding of the surgical team to the study's purpose was implemented to reduce performance bias.

Data Collection: Data collection was carried out using a standardized form that included demographic details, clinical history, and preoperative imaging findings. Adhesions were detected and staged preoperatively using imaging techniques and were confirmed intraoperatively.

Procedure: Participants underwent routine preoperative evaluations, including clinical examination and imaging studies such as ultrasonography or MRI. Based on the findings, patients were categorized into the case and control groups. The presence and extent of adhesions were classified according to a predefined staging system. During laparoscopic cholecystectomy, the intraoperative findings were recorded and compared with the preoperative staging.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and clinical characteristics. Chi-square and independent t-tests compared categorical and continuous variables between case and control groups, with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. Logistic regression identified predictors of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy, providing insights into the impact of adhesions on surgical complexity.

Results

A total of 50 participants were enrolled in the study, including 40 females (80%) aged 30 to 50 years and 10 males (20%) aged 45 to 55 years. The mean age of the female participants was 42.5 ± 5.8 years, while the mean age of the male participants was 50.2 ± 3.4 years.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Characteristic	Females (n=40)	Males (n=10)	Total (n=50)
Mean Age (years)	42.5 ± 5.8	50.2 ± 3.4	44.1 ± 6.7
Age Range (years)	30-50	45-55	30-55
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.3 ± 3.4	28.1 ± 2.9	27.5 ± 3.3
Co-morbidities (%)	15 (37.5%)	5 (50%)	20 (40%)

Adhesions were preoperatively detected in 28 participants (56%) through imaging studies. Among these, 22 were females and 6 were males.

The staging of adhesions was categorized into three stages:

- **Stage 1 (Mild Adhesions):** 14 participants (28%)
- **Stage 2 (Moderate Adhesions):** 9 participants (18%)
- **Stage 3 (Severe Adhesions):** 5 participants (10%).

Table 2: Preoperative Detection and Staging of Adhesions

Adhesion Stage	Females (n=40)	Males (n=10)	Total (n=50)
No Adhesions	18 (45%)	4 (40%)	22 (44%)
Stage 1 (Mild)	12 (30%)	2 (20%)	14 (28%)
Stage 2 (Moderate)	7 (17.5%)	2 (20%)	9 (18%)
Stage 3 (Severe)	3 (7.5%)	2 (20%)	5 (10%)

During laparoscopic cholecystectomy, adhesions were confirmed in 26 participants (52%). The accuracy of preoperative detection was assessed, showing a sensitivity of 92.9% and a specificity of 90.9%.

Table 3: Intraoperative Findings

Preoperative vs. Intraoperative Adhesion Detection	Present Intraoperatively (n=26)	Absent Intraoperatively (n=24)	Total (n=50)
Preoperatively Detected	24 (92.9%)	4 (16.7%)	28
Preoperatively Not Detected	2 (7.1%)	20 (83.3%)	22

The difficulty of LC was classified based on operative time and intraoperative complications. Difficult procedures were defined as those requiring more than 90 minutes of operative time or encountering significant complications.

- **Difficult LC:** 14 participants (28%)
- **Standard LC:** 36 participants (72%)

A strong correlation was found between the severity of adhesions and the difficulty of the procedure. Logistic regression analysis showed that participants with Stage 3 adhesions had an odds ratio of 4.8 (95% CI: 2.1-11.0) for a difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) compared to those without adhesions.

Table 4: Difficulty of Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

Adhesion Stage	Difficult Procedures (n=14)	Standard Procedures (n=36)	Total (n=50)
No Adhesions	2 (14.3%)	20 (55.6%)	22 (44%)
Stage 1 (Mild)	3 (21.4%)	11 (30.6%)	14 (28%)
Stage 2 (Moderate)	4 (28.6%)	5 (13.9%)	9 (18%)
Stage 3 (Severe)	5 (35.7%)	0 (0%)	5 (10%)

Statistical Analysis: The chi-square test showed a significant association between the presence of adhesions and the difficulty of the laparoscopic cholecystectomy ($p=0.003$). The independent t-test indicated a significant difference in operative time between participants with and without adhesions ($p=0.001$). Logistic regression analysis identified the stage of adhesions as a significant predictor of surgical difficulty ($p<0.01$).

This data demonstrates the importance of preoperative adhesion staging in predicting the complexity of laparoscopic cholecystectomy and highlights the need for careful preoperative planning in patients with detected adhesions.

Discussion

The study involved 50 participants, with a majority being female (80%). The mean age for females was 42.5 years, while males had a mean age of 50.2 years. Preoperative imaging detected adhesions in 56% of the participants, with a greater prevalence among females. The adhesions were categorized into three stages, with mild adhesions being the

most common. Intraoperative findings confirmed adhesions in 52% of participants, demonstrating a high accuracy of preoperative detection, with a sensitivity of 92.9% and specificity of 90.9%.

The study revealed a significant relationship between the severity of adhesions and the difficulty of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Difficult procedures were more likely in participants with severe adhesions, particularly those classified as Stage 3. Statistical analysis supported these findings, with chi-square tests showing a significant association between adhesion presence and surgical difficulty, and logistic regression indicating that the stage of adhesions was a strong predictor of operative challenges.

These results suggest that preoperative detection and staging of adhesions are crucial for anticipating the complexity of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Patients with severe adhesions are at a higher risk for difficult surgeries.

Modern preoperative diagnostic methods for laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) have improved

the ability to predict surgical difficulty, especially when adhesions are present. In a paper it was described there is a unique technique for preoperatively identifying and categorising gallbladder adhesions using Virtual Touch Imaging (VTI) based on Acoustic Radiation Force Impulse (ARFI). According to the study, the new Adhesion Detection and Staging (ADS) approach outperformed the traditional scoring system in terms of accuracy when it came to forecasting challenging (LCs). Compared to previous approaches, which had a sensitivity of 60.9%, the ADS classification demonstrated a sensitivity of 91% and an accuracy of 96% [5].

The significance of clinical and ultrasonographic data in forecasting the difficulty of LCs in a comparable study was demonstrated. According to the study, having a history of acute cholecystitis, being older, and being male raised the risk of having a challenging surgery. According to the findings, preoperative evaluation that takes these aspects into account may aid in better preparing for any intraoperative [6].

It was investigated that artificial intelligence (AI) can be used in order to evaluate the complexity of LCs in the early stages of surgery. With an accuracy of 88% in identifying challenging situations, the AI-based model showed promising result in predicting the degree of difficulty in performing laparoscopic procedures through the analysis of endoscopic video data. According to this study, this technology has the potential to improve surgical planning and decision-making [7].

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